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Challenges facing agricultural cooperatives in Mediterranean countries

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural cooperatives are vital to the Mediterranean region, enhancing farmers' market access, bargaining power, and innovation. However, they face significant challenges threatening their sustainability. This paper examines these challenges in France, Greece, Italy, Spain, and Türkiye using a qualitative approach that integrates insights from Solution Hub discussions and interviews with cooperative leaders, experts, and policy-makers. It identifies common challenges—governance inefficiencies, financial instability, climate change impacts, and generational renewal—alongside country-specific obstacles shaped by distinct socio-economic, environmental, and political contexts. Governance inefficiencies, including slow decision-making and under-representation of women and youth, are pervasive but manifest differently across countries. Financial instability, driven by market volatility and limited credit access, is particularly acute in Greece and Türkiye. Climate change poses serious threats, with France focusing on decarbonization and agro-ecological transitions, while Greece and Türkiye grapple with water scarcity and extreme weather. Demographic shifts, including rural depopulation and an aging workforce, exacerbate these challenges, especially in Italy and Spain. This study contributes to the literature by providing a comparative analysis of Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives, addressing a gap in research that often focuses on single-country studies. It underscores the need for context-specific strategies, recognizing that while some challenges are shared, their intensity and manifestations vary. The findings highlight the crucial role of cooperatives in addressing climate change and rural depopulation—areas often overlooked in the literature. Practical implications include targeted interventions, capacity-building, and supportive legal frameworks to enhance cooperative resilience. By fostering innovation, inclusivity, and regional collaboration, stakeholders can strengthen these essential institutions.

1. Introduction

Agricultural cooperatives play a pivotal role in the rural economies of many countries, serving as vital mechanisms for improving farmers' access to markets, enhancing their bargaining power, and fostering knowledge exchange and innovation (Bijman et al., 2012a,b; Ajates, 2020b). There is a substantial body of empirical work documenting the

positive effect of co-operatives on various farm outcomes (e.g., Akinola et al., 2023; Grashuis and Higuchi, 2023; Taniu et al., 2024). Despite their significance,¹ these cooperatives face a myriad of challenges that threaten their long-term sustainability and effectiveness (Sexton and Iskow, 1993; Cook, 2018; Iliopoulos and Valentinov, 2018a, 2018b). This paper examines the challenges confronting agricultural cooperatives in five Mediterranean countries—France, Greece, Italy,

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E-mail addresses: iliopoulos@elgo.gr (C. Iliopoulos), itheodorakopoulou@elgo.gr (I. Theodorakopoulou), mgdiaz@uniovi.es (M. Gonzalez Diaz), maryline.filippi@agroparitech.fr (M. Filippi), umberto.nizza@unito.it (U. Nizza), tektas@bogazici.edu.tr (A. Tektas).¹ For context, there are approximately 3669 agricultural cooperatives in Spain, 4268 in Italy, 2100 in France (plus 11,260 cooperatives for the shared use of agricultural machinery-CUMA), 1095 in Greece, and 11,754 in Türkiye; the sample presented in Table 1 is therefore illustrative rather than representative (Observatorio Socioeconómico del Cooperativismo Agroalimentario Español, 2023; Licciardo and Fontanari, 2024; La Coopération Agricole, 2024; MADF, 2025; MAF, 2024).<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2026.104004>

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Spain, and Türkiye—drawing on insights from two primary data sources: participatory discussions in Solution Hubs and in-depth interviews with cooperative leaders, experts, and policymakers. By adopting a qualitative research approach, this study captures the subjective and context-specific dimensions of these challenges, offering a detailed comprehension of the complexities faced by cooperatives in diverse socio-economic, environmental, and political contexts.

Agricultural cooperatives are member-owned and member-controlled organizations that enable farmers to jointly procure inputs, market outputs, and provide services that would be difficult or costly to obtain individually. From an organizational economics perspective, they are distinct in that ownership, control, and benefit rights are vested in the same group—patron-members—who both supply resources to and transact with the cooperative (Hansmann, 1996; Cook, 1995). This dual role of members as users and owners shapes the governance and contractual design of cooperatives, influencing how they mitigate transaction costs, address market failures, and align incentives (Cook and Iliopoulos, 2000; 2016; Iliopoulos and Cook, 2023). Consequently, cooperatives can be viewed as institutional responses to organizational and market inefficiencies, yet their unique property rights structure also creates internal challenges that affect their evolution and long-term sustainability.

The Mediterranean region, with its rich agricultural heritage and diverse cultural landscapes, presents a unique setting for studying agricultural cooperatives. These organizations are not only economic entities but also social institutions that contribute to rural development, community cohesion, and environmental sustainability. However, they operate in an increasingly challenging environment characterized by climate change, market volatility, regulatory complexities, and demographic shifts. Existing literature has documented the challenges faced by agricultural cooperatives, particularly in terms of governance inefficiencies, financial instability, and market-related barriers (Arcidiacono, 2018; Filippi, 2020; Lucas-Martínez et al., 2020; Mozas Moral and Fernández Uclés, 2022). However, much of this research has focused on individual countries or specific sectors, leaving a gap in understanding the broader regional dynamics and the interplay between common and country-specific challenges. Compared to the extensive literature on cooperatives in Northern Europe, North America, and Latin America, Mediterranean cooperatives remain understudied, despite their central role in EU agriculture and rural development. This scarcity of comparative regional studies leaves important gaps in understanding how systemic challenges play out in Mediterranean contexts. This paper seeks to address this gap by providing a comparative analysis of cooperatives across five Mediterranean countries, highlighting both shared obstacles and unique contextual factors.

This study is grounded in the theoretical frameworks of organizational economics (Coase, 1937; (Williamson, 1985)) and institutional theory (Hansmann, 1996). Organizational economics provides a lens for understanding the transaction costs and governance inefficiencies faced by cooperatives, such as slow decision-making and low-powered incentives. Institutional theory, on the other hand, helps explain how regulatory environments and institutional pressures shape cooperative behavior, particularly in navigating complex legal frameworks and market failures. Together, these frameworks offer a comprehensive basis for analyzing the organizational, market, and institutional challenges confronting Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives. These frameworks are particularly relevant in the Mediterranean context, where cooperatives must navigate complex governance structures, market failures, and regulatory environments (Bijman and Iliopoulos, 2014; Sánchez-Navarro et al., 2019). However, while existing literature has explored these challenges in depth, there is limited research on how they manifest differently across countries with varying socio-economic and political contexts. This paper contributes to filling this gap by providing a cross-country analysis that highlights the diversity of challenges and the need for tailored strategies to address them.

By integrating multiple data sources and perspectives, this study

offers a holistic understanding of the challenges for cooperatives in the region, contributing to their resilience and sustainability in an evolving agricultural landscape, understood here in line with the FAO's framework, which emphasizes economic viability, environmental stewardship, and social inclusion. The research makes several key contributions to the academic literature. First, it provides a comprehensive, cross-country analysis of the challenges faced by agricultural cooperatives in the Mediterranean, filling a gap in the existing literature that often focuses on single-country or sector-specific studies. Second, it highlights the importance of context-specific strategies, emphasizing that while some challenges are common across the region, their manifestations and intensity vary significantly by country. Third, it underscores the role of cooperatives in addressing emerging issues such as climate change and rural depopulation, areas that have received limited attention in the literature on agricultural cooperatives. Finally, the study offers practical insights for policymakers and cooperative leaders, advocating for targeted interventions that address both shared and unique obstacles, thereby enhancing the resilience and sustainability of Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives.

The paper is structured as follows. Following this introduction, Section 2 provides a theoretical background, synthesizing existing literature on the challenges faced by agricultural cooperatives, categorized into three types of challenges: organizational challenges, market- and industry-related, and institutional and legal environment-related. Section 3 outlines the methodology, detailing the qualitative research approach, the use of Solution Hubs and interviews, and the data analysis process. Section 4 presents the results, divided into common challenges across the five countries and country-specific challenges identified through Solution Hubs and interviews. Section 5 discusses the findings, relating them to the existing literature, comparing cross-country and data source perspectives, and drawing implications for theory, practice, and policy. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper, summarizing the key findings and highlighting the need for context-specific strategies to address the challenges faced by Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives.

2. Literature review: challenges facing agricultural cooperatives

Agricultural cooperatives are distinctive member-owned enterprises that pool resources, share risks, and provide collective services to farmers (Ajates, 2020b; Bijman and Iliopoulos, 2014). Their governance rests on the democratic principle of one-member-one-vote, which differentiates them from investor-owned firms but also generates unique costs and inefficiencies (Hansmann, 1996). Despite their pivotal role in improving market access, bargaining power, and knowledge exchange, cooperatives worldwide face multiple challenges threatening their long-term viability (e.g. Bijman et al., 2014). These challenges can be grouped into three categories: (1) organizational challenges, (2) market- and industry-related challenges, and (3) institutional and legal challenges. While much of the literature has been developed in non-Mediterranean contexts, there is a small but growing body of research on cooperatives in Mediterranean countries. This section reviews both strands, highlighting the scarcity of Mediterranean-specific studies and thereby motivating this paper's comparative contribution.

2.1. Organizational challenges in agricultural cooperatives

Organizational economics (Coase, 1937) conceptualizes the firm as a governance structure designed to minimize transaction costs. For cooperatives, however, ownership, control, and benefit rights are widely dispersed, creating distinctive organizational costs. These include both market contracting costs (coordination and motivation) and ownership costs (monitoring managers, collective decision-making, and risk-bearing) (Hansmann, 1996; Milgrom and Roberts, 1992).

Scholars distinguish between formation costs (incurred in designing governance structures, establishing communication channels, raising

equity, and defining membership rules) and maintenance costs (incurred in daily operations and long-term sustainability) (Bradburd and Mead, 1982; Iliopoulos and Cook, 2023). Formation costs determine whether cooperatives are created at all, while maintenance costs often intensify over time as member heterogeneity increases (Olson, 1965; Ostrom, 1990).

Maintenance challenges manifest in well-documented governance problems (Cook, 1995; Fulton and Hueth, 2009; Iliopoulos and Valentinov, 2018a; Iliopoulos and Cook, 2023; Cook, 2018).

- **Free rider problems:** both internal (new members enjoy the same benefits as founders) and external (non-members benefit without contributing).
- **Horizon problems:** reluctance to invest in long-term projects when members' expected benefits are short-lived.
- **Portfolio problems:** tied patronage and investment lead to suboptimal risk-taking.
- **Risk-bearing constraints:** limited member equity reduces capacity for growth.
- **Managerial opportunism and monitoring costs:** boards may lack resources to supervise management effectively.
- **Collective decision-making costs:** heterogeneous preferences increase conflict, delay, and inefficiency.
- **Influence costs:** lobbying and factionalism distort cooperative decisions.

Empirical research confirms that such inefficiencies threaten cooperative performance. Fulton and Hueth (2009) show how weak governance undermines decision-making, while Grashuis and Cook (2018) link organizational bottlenecks to the failure of new-generation cooperatives in the U.S. Evidence from developing countries indicates that membership can enhance productivity and welfare, but only when governance mechanisms are robust (Akinola et al., 2023; Taniu et al., 2024).

To address these challenges, cooperatives employ tinkering and reinvention strategies (Cook and Iliopoulos, 2016; Cook, 2018). Common responses include.

- **User alignment** (e.g., base capital plans, delivery rights, proportional voting).
- **Member retention** (e.g., binding contracts, member training, loyalty programs).
- **Supply-demand balancing** (e.g., exclusive marketing agreements, defined membership, joint ventures).
- **Transparency solutions** (e.g., clearer performance metrics, differentiated contracts).

When these incremental solutions fail, more fundamental responses are required: reinvention (new hybrid models), spawning (creating new organizations), or exit (conversion or liquidation).

Case study evidence highlights how these problems play out in practice. For example, Conserve Italia used user alignment and transparency solutions to strengthen governance (Bono and Iliopoulos, 2012). Nordmilch in Germany restructured through reinvention, adopting a corporate governance model (Hanisch and Müller, 2012). U.S. cooperatives like Blue Diamond and Florida's Natural introduced transparency and member-retention solutions to maintain competitiveness (Cook and Iliopoulos, 2016).

In the Mediterranean context, organizational challenges are widespread but understudied comparatively. French cooperatives use the territory to respond to the risk of tension with their members, linked to their increasing size and complexity. Spanish and Italian cooperatives often struggle to balance democratic governance with the need for professionalized management (Lucas-Martínez et al., 2020; Arcidiacono, 2018). In Greece, chronic governance inefficiencies, weak member commitment, and limited strategic vision persist (Iliopoulos, 2013). In

Türkiye, the legacy of politically influenced cooperative structures has eroded member trust (Özpençe, 2017). These cases illustrate how organizational costs are shaped by both internal governance dynamics and broader institutional contexts.

2.2. Market- and industry-related challenges

2.2.1. Market-related challenges

Agricultural cooperatives are often formed to counter market failures and enhance farmers' bargaining power (Sexton and Iskow, 1988; Cook, 1995). Farmers face structural disadvantages in agricultural markets due to product perishability, localized supply chains, and specialized production investments, all of which make them vulnerable to oligopsony power from processors and retailers (Sexton, 1990). Cooperatives mitigate these disadvantages by pooling supply, reducing transaction costs, and providing countervailing power against concentrated downstream firms.

Market failures impose costs such as double monopoly mark-ups, lack of countervailing power, missing services, contractual incompleteness, and problems of adverse selection and moral hazard (Williamson, 1985; Barzel, 1989; Hansmann, 1996). By acting collectively, cooperatives attempt to lower these costs and secure stable outlets, fairer prices, and improved access to information and credit.

Empirical evidence, however, shows persistent challenges. Gray and Kraenzle (2002) document that low commodity prices, global competition, and rising costs were the most pressing problems for U.S. cooperatives, and these remain central issues worldwide. Pujara (2016) highlights similar problems in developing-country settings, where farmer cooperatives often lack marketing skills, face difficulties in building trust among members, and struggle with bargaining power in fragmented markets. Brazilian evidence points to the importance of trust and loyalty: Leite et al. (2021) show that opportunism and member disengagement threaten continuity, while cooperation enables smallholders to access otherwise restricted markets.

In Mediterranean countries, market-related challenges are well illustrated in Spain and Italy, where cooperatives dominate fruit, vegetable, and wine sectors but struggle with competition from investor-owned firms and international supply chains (Arcidiacono, 2018; Lucas-Martínez et al., 2020). With three out of four farmers and one out of three food brands, French agricultural cooperatives are key players in agriculture and agri-food. At the same time, they face intra-cooperative and external environment challenges (Filippi, 2014). In Greece, cooperatives face structural weaknesses in marketing channels and limited countervailing power vis-à-vis large buyers (Iliopoulos, 2013; Benos et al., 2016). In Türkiye, liberalization reduced state support and left cooperatives exposed to market volatility and retailer concentration (Özpençe, 2017; Sevinç, 2021).

Thus, while cooperatives are founded to solve market failures, they face enduring challenges of low commodity prices, buyer concentration, global competition, and lack of marketing skills—problems that are especially acute in fragmented Mediterranean agri-food markets.

2.2.2. Industry-related challenges

Beyond market failures, agricultural cooperatives must adapt to broader industry transformations. Globalization, consolidation, and retail restructuring have intensified competitive pressures. Hansen (2009) identifies globalization as a double-edged sword: while it offers new opportunities, it also challenges cooperatives' traditional member-based structures, particularly in accessing capital for international expansion. Danish experience shows that cooperatives with strong capital bases and global strategies can thrive, but weaker ones are left behind.

Industry consolidation and retail concentration also reshape cooperative strategies. Hendrikse (2006) emphasizes that growing heterogeneity among farmers and the rise of supermarkets force cooperatives to adopt differentiated governance models, including tradable delivery

rights and proportional voting. In the U.S., Gray and Kraenzle (2002) found that cooperatives increasingly relied on mergers, joint ventures, and vertical integration to survive. Similar dynamics occur in Europe, where cooperatives in dairy and wine sectors have pursued cross-border mergers and hybrid organizational forms (Bijman and Iliopoulos, 2014).

At the same time, industry-related pressures create internal strains. Balancing professional management with democratic governance remains difficult, especially when globalization requires faster decision-making and higher risk-taking. Evidence from Mediterranean countries confirms these challenges: in Spain, fruit and vegetable cooperatives have consolidated to compete with supermarket chains, but member loyalty has weakened (Giagnocavo et al., 2012; Lucas-Martínez et al., 2020). Faced with the dilemma of having to reconcile their dual nature, striking a balance between their social and commercial functions while complying with standards or regulations and meeting the needs of their members, French agricultural cooperatives are caught between competitiveness and commoditization, with a decline in member engagement (Filippi, 2020). In Italy, wine cooperatives struggle to maintain local embeddedness while integrating into global value chains (Arcidiacono, 2018). In Greece and Türkiye, limited capital, small scale, and dependence on state policy hinder competitiveness at the industry level (Iliopoulos, 2013; Sevinç, 2021).

In summary, industry-related challenges revolve around consolidation, globalization, and retail restructuring. Successful cooperatives respond by innovating governance, forming alliances, and professionalizing management, but these strategies are unevenly adopted across regions.

The literature confirms that while cooperatives help farmers address market failures and adapt to structural changes, most empirical evidence comes from North America, Northern Europe, or developing-country settings. Research on Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives remains comparatively scarce, fragmented across single-country or sectoral studies, and often descriptive rather than comparative or theory-driven. Spanish fruit and vegetable cooperatives, Italian wine consortia, Greek, French and Turkish multipurpose cooperatives, and French dairy and cereals cooperatives provide important examples, but no integrated cross-country perspective exists. This gap underscores the need for comparative Mediterranean analyses—such as the present study—to better understand how regional cooperatives navigate market and industry-related challenges in contexts of strong global competition, fragmented governance, and institutional complexity.

2.3. Institutional and legal challenges

Institutional economics highlights the critical role of legal and regulatory frameworks in shaping cooperative performance (North, 1990). Because cooperatives combine features of both associations and business firms, they are particularly sensitive to institutional design. Supportive cooperative law can enable professionalization, innovation, and long-term investment, whereas restrictive, fragmented, or unstable regulation can undermine member trust, limit access to resources, and constrain competitiveness (Henry, 2012; Bijman and Iliopoulos, 2014; Dohmworth and Hanisch, 2019).

Across contexts, institutional and legal barriers take multiple forms. Outdated or inadequate laws governing cooperative formation, registration, and operation hinder the development of robust cooperative enterprises (Iliopoulos, 2013). Restrictive membership criteria, cumbersome registration procedures, and ambiguous governance requirements can deter farmers from forming cooperatives or limit their ability to operate efficiently (Henry, 2012). The legal status of cooperatives also strongly influences their access to essential resources such as land, credit, and market infrastructure (Ajates, 2023; Piñeiro et al., 2021). In many cases, limited access to credit and financial services reflects regulatory constraints and risk-averse lending practices by banks unfamiliar with cooperative ownership structures, restricting investment in technology, infrastructure, and market development

(Grashuis and Jacobs, 2024; García Pérez et al., 2024).

Beyond legal frameworks, weak governance structures, leadership deficits, and internal conflicts exacerbate institutional challenges. These undermine effective decision-making and erode member trust and engagement (Iliopoulos and Cook, 2023; Cook, 2018; Fulton and Hueth, 2009). Disparities in members' knowledge, skills, and financial resources can create power imbalances, thus, marginalizing certain groups and weakening inclusive governance. Addressing these shortcomings requires capacity-building initiatives, leadership training programs, and transparent practices that empower members, improve accountability, and ensure equitable participation (Ajates, 2020a).

Comparative research outside the Mediterranean confirms these dynamics. In Latin America, Brazil illustrates how legal frameworks that support transparency and member rights foster successful cooperatives, while weak enforcement encourages opportunism (Leite et al., 2021). In Africa, cooperatives collapsed once state subsidies were withdrawn, revealing the risks of excessive political interference and dependence (Francesconi and Ruben, 2012). These cases underline that institutional quality is a decisive factor for cooperative sustainability.

In Mediterranean countries, institutional and legal weaknesses surface in diverse ways, though the evidence is fragmented and mostly country-specific.

- In France, cooperatives operate under a complex regulatory environment shaped by both EU and national policies. While measures such as the *Loi d'Orientation Agricole* have supported cooperative expansion, compliance requirements and frequent policy changes create bureaucratic burdens that favor large cooperatives and strain smaller ones. Recent reforms promoting gender-inclusive governance and training for youth and women represent promising innovations (Filippi, 2014).
- In Greece, unstable cooperative law, frequent legislative changes, and land fragmentation discourage long-term planning and efficient organization. Limited institutional support and weak coordination among cooperatives further constrain competitiveness (Patronis and Mavreas, 2004; Iliopoulos, 2013).
- In Italy, bureaucratic hurdles, rigid statutes, and capacity constraints hinder innovation and flexibility. High compliance costs and limited resources reduce the ability of cooperatives to modernize governance or invest in training programs (Arcidiacono, 2018).
- In Spain, rigid administrative processes, complex aid allocation procedures, and regulatory inefficiencies reduce cooperative agility. Streamlining governance frameworks and cooperative bylaws has been identified as a key priority for enhancing resilience (Giagnocavo et al., 2012; Vargas-Vasserot, 2021).
- In Türkiye, political instability, excessive bureaucracy, insecure land tenure rights, and climate-related risks undermine cooperative development. Frequent shifts in government policy disrupt long-term planning, while weak enforcement of cooperative law perpetuates inefficiency (Özpençe, 2017; Sevinç, 2021).

Institutional and legal challenges are central to cooperative viability worldwide, but evidence for Mediterranean countries remains fragmented across single-country and sectoral studies. France highlights the complexity of regulatory compliance, Greece the destabilizing effects of legal instability, Italy the burden of bureaucracy and capacity gaps, Spain the inefficiencies of aid allocation and governance frameworks, and Türkiye the legacies of political interference and weak enforcement. Despite these insights, no systematic cross-country framework exists. This gap underscores the importance of comparative Mediterranean studies—such as the present paper—that situate national experiences within a broader regional perspective.

3. Methodology and data

This study employs a qualitative research approach to identify the

primary challenges confronting agricultural cooperatives in the Mediterranean region. Qualitative methods are particularly well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena, as they allow researchers to capture subjective meanings, contextual nuances, and emergent themes (Woods, 2010; Strijker et al., 2020). Existing research on the challenges faced by agricultural cooperatives often relies on cross-sectional qualitative methods, including semi-structured interviews and case studies. For instance, Hayden et al. (2024) use semi-structured interviews to analyze the benefits and barriers of collaborative farming arrangements, while Levai et al. (2024) employ a participatory approach involving workshops with cooperative managers and members. Similarly, Dumitru et al. (2022) conduct an in-depth investigation into the underdevelopment of agricultural cooperatives in Romania. Piñeiro et al. (2021) utilize surveys to explore cooperative managers' perspectives on joint cropland management strategies. Other studies, such as those by Kalo-giannidis et al. (2024), Olaoye et al. (2024), and Leite et al. (2021), rely on cross-sectional surveys and descriptive analyses to examine the role of cooperatives in sustainable agriculture and the challenges faced by smallholder farmers. (Sevinç, 2021) further complements this body of work by analyzing farmers' perceptions of agricultural cooperatives through face-to-face surveys and regression analysis. Another example is collecting data from print media publications, as demonstrated by Grashuis and Cook (2018) in an analysis of challenges common to so-called new generation cooperatives.

Qualitative methods are especially relevant for understanding the multifaceted challenges faced by cooperatives, as these challenges are shaped by the perspectives of members, managers, and stakeholders (Ajates, 2017). A qualitative approach captures the subjective and context-specific dimensions of these challenges but also generates context-specific insights that are critical given the broad geographical scope of the research (Spain, France, Italy, Greece, and Türkiye) (Aspers and Corte, 2019; Camfield et al., 2009).

3.1. Solution Hubs: A methodological innovation

A key methodological innovation of this study is the use of Solution Hubs (SHs), which are both physical and conceptual spaces where cooperative leaders (board chairs and managers) engage in a facilitated process to co-create solutions to their cooperatives' challenges. Grounded in Theory U (Scharmer, 2018), SHs represent a bottom-up, participatory approach to research and solution design. The SHs were designed following the logic of living labs. In practice, we organized several meetings in the form of focus groups, facilitated by researchers and a professional SH leader. Researchers attended these meetings, documented discussions with notes and flipcharts, and, where permitted, audio-recorded them. Outputs were transcribed, translated into English, and coded. They were facilitated by the research team and a professional SH Leader, guiding participants through a structured process that includes data collection, reflection, and co-creation. This approach not only empowers participants to contribute to problem-solving actively but also ensures that the solutions generated are contextually relevant and actionable. By integrating SHs into the research design, this study advances a novel methodology that bridges the gap between academic inquiry and practical problem-solving in the context of agricultural cooperatives.

3.2. Research design and data collection

The research design involved two primary data sources: (1) outcomes from SH meetings and (2) semi-structured interviews with stakeholders. To ensure methodological consistency, researchers from each participating country were trained in the study's protocols. Purposive sampling was used to select SH participants, ensuring that respondents were directly relevant to the research question and capable of providing valuable insights (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). Purposive sampling, often referred to as a judgmental procedure, relies on the

researcher's discretion to select individuals and instances that can offer the most useful data to meet the study's goals (Paraschou and Sergaki, 2024). This technique is widely used in studies related to the challenges and performance of agricultural cooperatives (Mundia et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2022; Paraschou and Sergaki, 2024; Dhakal and Mueser, 2023).

Data collection through SH meetings took place between August 2022 and February 2023 across all participating countries, with at least one meeting in each country dedicated to identifying the most pressing organizational and managerial challenges faced by cooperatives.

To complement the SH data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with knowledgeable stakeholders, including cooperative leaders, policymakers, and industry experts. These interviews aimed to triangulate data sources and perspectives, thereby enriching the study's understanding of cooperative challenges (Denzin and Lincoln, 1998). A total of 50 interviews were conducted across the five countries: ten in France, ten in Greece, eight in Italy, fourteen in Spain, and eight in Türkiye. The international dimension of this study enhances the robustness of the findings by enabling cross-cultural comparisons and highlighting contextual variations in cooperative challenges (Hantrais, 2014). The selected countries represent historically significant agricultural cultures, making them ideal for exploring the intersection of tradition and modernity in cooperative management. Table 1 summarizes the profile of SH participants and interviewees by country.

Overall, the sample reflects the diversity of cooperative governance roles across the five countries and provided a robust basis for the subsequent thematic analysis.

3.3. Data processing and analysis

Data processing followed a rigorous and transparent protocol to ensure the credibility and reliability of the findings. Both SH meeting outputs and interview data were meticulously documented through research team notes, flipchart posters completed by SH participants, and audio recordings of interviews. Summaries of the recordings were transcribed in the local language and subsequently translated into English. Data from the SH meetings were organized into Microsoft Word tables, with one table dedicated to cataloging challenges faced by Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives, each column representing a different country.

A similar protocol was applied to the interview data. Transcripts were translated into English and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase thematic analysis framework: (1) familiarization with the data, (2) initial coding, (3) identifying themes, (4) reviewing themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) reporting. Given the study's international scope, thematic analysis was complemented by cross-country comparisons to identify similarities and differences in the challenges faced by cooperatives. The three-category framework (organizational, market/industry-related, and institutional/legal) was defined before the Solution Hubs and interviews, based on the literature. While this pre-definition could potentially bias categorization, participants were not prompted with the categories, and triangulation across SH and interview data helped mitigate this risk. Reflexivity and peer debriefing were integral to the analysis process, further enhancing the study's credibility.

Taken together, the SH discussions and interviews yielded rich qualitative material that, once categorized within the three challenge areas, provided the foundation for the results presented in the next section.

4. Results

The analysis of Solution Hub discussions and interviews revealed three broad categories of challenges confronting agricultural cooperatives in the Mediterranean: organizational, market and industry, and institutional/legal. These categories were defined a priori on the

Table 1
Sample of cooperatives and participants in Solution Hubs and interviews.

Country	No. of Cooperatives	Board members & Chairs	Managers	Officers	Industry	Interviewees
France	4	4	6	0	Multipurpose, Wine	10 (5 experts, 4 leaders, 1 policymaker)
Greece	7	10	5	0	Cereals, Cotton, Dairy, Raisins	10 (3 experts, 5 leaders, 2 policymakers)
Italy	9	5	6	3	Wine	8 (3 experts, 2 leaders, 3 policymakers)
Spain	8	3	7	0	Dairy, Multipurpose	14 (6 experts, 5 leaders, 3 policymakers)
Türkiye	4	6	15	0	Olive, Olive Oil, Sunflower	8 (2 experts, 5 leaders, 1 policymaker)
Total	32	28	39	3	n/a	50 interviewees (19 experts, 21 leaders, 10 policymakers)

Notes: In Türkiye, the number of participants was higher relative to cooperatives because multiple managers from the same cooperative attended. In Italy, “policymakers” refers to parliamentarians and administrative staff of cooperatives’ confederation. In some cases (Greece and Türkiye), more than one board member from the same cooperative participated, which explains why the number of board chairs exceeds the number of cooperatives. No monetary remuneration was provided; participation was voluntary, and participants covered their own travel expenses.

basis of the literature (see Section 2) and guided the thematic coding. While many issues are interlinked, we assigned each challenge to the category where participants placed the greatest emphasis. Illustrative examples from each country are presented to show variation in how these challenges manifest across contexts.

4.1. Organizational challenges

Across all five countries, participants consistently identified internal organizational challenges as a central threat to cooperative sustainability. These challenges cluster around three interrelated issues: (i) governance inefficiencies and gaps in professionalization, (ii) weak member engagement and declining trust, and (iii) difficulties related to generational renewal and inclusivity. While these issues are present in all national contexts, their intensity and specific manifestations vary across countries. The following subsections illustrate how these organizational challenges emerge in practice, drawing on evidence from Solution Hub discussions and interviews.

Governance inefficiencies and professionalization gaps. These issues were consistently framed by participants as structural constraints that limit cooperatives’ ability to respond effectively to growing organizational complexity, competitive pressures, and strategic demands. Many cooperatives struggle with slow decision-making, outdated governance structures, and insufficient managerial expertise. Greek and Turkish participants in particular described difficulties in recruiting skilled staff and board members capable of managing increasingly complex cooperative operations. As one board chair from Greece noted: “We often lack managers with the right skills. Many of us on the board are farmers first, but we don’t have the training to run an enterprise of this size.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Board chair, Greece]. The same problem was echoed in the answer of a Turkish cooperative manager: “The managers of individual cooperatives are also farmers. Their level of education is low and this leads to managing the cooperative in an inefficient way.” [Interview – Cooperative manager, Türkiye].

An Italian cooperative manager highlighted the slow decision-making process constraining agricultural cooperatives in the country: “Managing a cooperative is truly challenging ... What I always see as the limit to change is the long process: first, you have to convince the members, then the board, and finally the employees. This creates a constant loop ... A dog with many masters dies of hunger.” [Interview – Cooperative Manager, Italy].

In France and Spain, the challenge was less about basic governance capacity and more about balancing democratic member control with the need for professionalized leadership. A Spanish legal advisor suggests that “There comes a time when you have to grow and organize yourself ... it is necessary to guarantee the uniqueness of the decisions of all owned IOFs with the SAT. This is how the members keep seeing the whole group as an associative and family-oriented organization.” [Interview – Cooperative Legal Advisor, Spain]. The French board chair of the apex cooperative body argued that “Agricultural cooperatives operate in a rapidly changing environment ... They are confronted with the logic of size in order to reach a critical mass and must therefore meet

more complex organizational challenges. To summarize, coping with the complexity of market changes, globalization, societal expectations, and ensuring governance with the right profiles, professionalization, and training.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, France].

Member engagement and trust. Participants described weak member engagement and declining trust as relational challenges that undermine collective action, weaken cooperative identity, and erode long-term organizational cohesion. Weak member commitment was reported as a recurring problem. Turkish participants emphasized low levels of trust in cooperatives, often linked to past negative experiences: “Previous experiences of members with cooperatives diminish their trust, making collective engagement harder to attain and weakening the cooperative’s chance of survival.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Türkiye, Cooperative expert].

Similarly, French interviewees noted that some members view cooperatives as commercial service providers rather than participatory organizations. As a cooperative board chair explained, “The cooperative is an extension of the members’ farms, and this is all the more difficult to get across to young members who see the cooperative as a captive client and who have no sense of the common good ... At a given moment, a member may feel more frustrated in his expectations, but he will always have a source of income at the end of the day.” [Interview – Cooperative chair, France].

In Italy and Spain, communication gaps between boards and members were seen as undermining cohesion. A board chair from Spain noted that “The challenge is to train the member ... Members only look at the price. It is necessary to involve the member because the connection that existed with the member is being lost.” [Interview – Cooperative Board Chair, Spain]. As a cooperative manager from Spain mentioned, “The big and young livestock farmers want to grow ... but they doubt whether the place to do it is the cooperative, because in the cooperative everyone is still treated equally.” [Interview – Cooperative Manager, Spain].

In Greece, individualism threatens cooperatives’ very existence. One expert commented that, “Members often prioritize their individual interests over the collective good, and this weakens the cooperative’s cohesion.” [Interview – Cooperative Leader, Greece].

Generational renewal and inclusivity. Difficulties related to generational renewal and inclusivity were interpreted as long-term threats to cooperative continuity, reflecting broader demographic shifts, changing values, and declining attractiveness of cooperative governance roles. The difficulty of attracting younger members and ensuring intergenerational succession emerged strongly in Italy and Spain, where rural depopulation and declining interest in farming exacerbate the issue. An Italian cooperative leader highlighted this issue: “I am concerned about the governance of cooperatives in the coming years. Even the more critical young people are not interested in joining the board, seeing it as a waste of time. We had four board members whose terms were expiring, and it took us six months to find replacements.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, Italy].

However, in France, “All board members are required to complete the SENEQUE diploma program, which provides cooperative administrators with the tools they need to ensure competitiveness, effective

governance, and efficient strategic management.” [Interview – Cooperative manager, France].

Underrepresentation of women in leadership roles was also raised, especially in Spain and France, though some participants pointed to emerging initiatives for gender-inclusive governance. For example, a French cooperative leader suggested that “... still need to take practical steps to increase the number of women serving on cooperative boards.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, France].

A Spanish cooperative leader commented on the impact of farmer individualism on cooperatives: “Often the effort it took to build the cooperative is not valued ... We have not been able to transmit that emotional element to young people, who have a more individualistic vision.” [Interview – Cooperative manager, Spain].

Another dimension of generational renewal was mentioned by an Italian cooperative leader: “Today, cooperatives suffer from a lack of attractiveness. Many people think that being an independent entrepreneur brings greater satisfaction. One of the key points for the future will be modernizing the way we present what it means to be a cooperative member today.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, Italy].

Similar issues are faced by Turkish agricultural cooperatives: “The agricultural population and the average age of cooperative members are increasing, while younger generations are less engaged in farming in Türkiye.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Türkiye].

4.2. Market and industry challenges

Beyond internal organizational issues, agricultural cooperatives across the Mediterranean face significant pressures arising from their market environment and broader industry transformations. Participants highlighted three main sets of challenges: (i) financial instability and persistent profitability pressures, (ii) climate change impacts and resource pressures, and (iii) labour shortages linked to rural depopulation and changing supply-chain dynamics. These challenges often interact with existing organizational weaknesses, amplifying their effects and constraining cooperatives’ strategic responses. The following analysis illustrates how these market and industry pressures affect cooperatives in different national contexts.

Financial instability and profitability pressures. Financial instability was portrayed as a persistent constraint on cooperative viability, limiting investment capacity and reinforcing short-term decision-making in an increasingly volatile market environment. Participants in Greece, Türkiye, and Spain stressed the difficulties of maintaining profitability in the face of low commodity prices, rising input costs, and limited access to credit. A cooperative manager from Greece suggested that “We cannot compete when input costs rise every year but the prices we get for our products stay the same. It leaves no room for investment.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Cooperative manager, Greece]. A Turkish cooperative manager referred to the reluctance of members to invest in their cooperative: “The number one challenge is difficulty in accessing cheap financing ... All money we earn goes to members and there is no money left for renewing the facility. Investment in agricultural infrastructure and technology is not sufficient.” [Interview – Cooperative Deputy GM, Türkiye].

In Italy, competition from non-cooperative buyers often forces cooperatives to prioritize short-term responses over long-term strategic investments: “Farmers tend to focus only on their own farm and the money they receive ... A member received an offer of €30,000 per hectare from a private buyer, and we can't compete with that. We have to work efficiently to increase our margin.” [Interview – Cooperative Member, Italy].

French participants added that stringent loan conditions and high compliance costs make long-term investment particularly challenging. As a manager suggested, “Until now, the cooperative has had few projections because it is difficult to establish budgets when developments are uncertain. Management is done on an almost day-to-day basis, and banks do not have adequate answers.” [Interview – Cooperative manager,

France].

Climate change and resource pressures. Climate-related pressures were framed as both immediate operational risks and strategic challenges, requiring adaptation investments that many cooperatives struggle to finance or coordinate collectively. Climate-related risks were consistently raised but with different emphases. Spanish participants described severe drought and water scarcity as urgent threats. Turkish cooperatives reported increasing vulnerability to extreme weather events. In France, the focus was on integrating decarbonization and carbon neutrality targets into cooperative strategies, requiring heavy investments. An expert noted that “The most urgent challenges are climate and food sovereignty. Cooperatives, because of their status, are in a specific position to make the link between production and the market and are key actors in the transitions of tomorrow.” [Interview – Legal Expert, France].

In Italy, by contrast, participants emphasized that the impact of climate change depends on specific production choices made by farmers. As one board chair argued, “Climate change is both a challenge and an opportunity for different grape varieties. For certain vineyards at lower altitudes, it will become more difficult because it will get too hot. However, varieties like Lagrein and Merlot thrive in higher temperatures.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, Italy].

Climate change adaptation was also linked to the size of cooperatives in Greece by an expert who stated that, “Climate change is a serious concern: water scarcity and extreme weather affect yields, and small cooperatives lack the resources to adapt quickly.” [Interview – Cooperative Expert, Greece].

Labor shortages and rural depopulation. Labor shortages and rural depopulation were widely seen as structural challenges that reduce productive capacity and exacerbate generational imbalances within cooperatives and their member base. Declining rural populations were frequently cited as a key factor reducing the available agricultural workforce. A cooperative leader commented that “Our members are leaving farming because it is no longer viable. Rural depopulation is hitting us very hard.” [Interview – Cooperative Leader, Greece].

Spanish and Turkish cooperatives reported particular difficulties in recruiting both seasonal farm labor and skilled technical staff. In Spain, a cooperative leader highlighted this issue: “One of the most important challenges is generational renewal ... more than 30 % of producers are over 65 ... there are fewer and fewer members ... which affects competitiveness.” [Interview – Director General of Agri-Food Cooperative Association, Spain]. Similarly, a technician from a local government provided a similar point of view: “All the livestock farmers are around 60 years old and have no replacements ... At 20, their sons and daughters are studying in the city ... we have, so to speak, encouraged them not to stay in the countryside!” [Interview – Technician (local government), Spain].

In Türkiye, cooperatives and their members suffer from the same issues: “There is a shortage of labor for basic agricultural and animal management tasks, due to an aging population and worker migration to cities for higher paying jobs.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Türkiye, Cooperative board chair].

In France, shortages extended to managerial positions, with cooperatives struggling to retain qualified professionals in rural areas. A board chair argued that “Unless we attract top-quality managers, the future will be very difficult competing with strong multinationals.” [Solution Hub meeting – Cooperative board chair, France].

Competition and supply chain pressures. Participants interpreted competition and supply chain pressures as asymmetrical power dynamics that weaken cooperatives’ bargaining positions and constrain their ability to secure fair prices for members. Market liberalization and retail concentration have increased competitive pressures across the region. In Türkiye, participants’ perception is that “The prices we announce become the market price. We are hurt by pricing policies followed by retailers ... Retailers dictate the price, and government efforts to suppress retail prices hurt farmers. At the end, farmers cannot

survive with such low prices.” [Interview – Cooperative manager, Türkiye].

Participating Italian wine cooperatives reported challenges in adapting to international value chains, while French cooperatives highlighted the dominance of supermarket chains in dictating pricing standards. A legal expert from France provided a grim view of a future without cooperatives: “If the cooperatives disappear, farmers will be faced with private operators. Their margin will be confiscated by large-scale distribution. Cooperatives protect farmers from the market and from being integrated by retailers upstream and downstream.” [Interview – Legal Expert, France].

4.3. Institutional and legal challenges

A third group of challenges identified by participants relates to the institutional and legal environment in which cooperatives operate. These challenges primarily concern (i) regulatory complexity and administrative burdens, (ii) limited institutional support and capacity gaps, and (iii) structural constraints related to land tenure and property rights. While such challenges are shaped by national legal frameworks, participants across countries emphasized their cumulative effect in generating uncertainty, discouraging long-term planning and weakening cooperative resilience. The following section presents country-specific illustrations of these institutional and legal constraints.

Regulatory complexity and bureaucracy. Regulatory complexity was consistently described as a source of uncertainty and administrative burden, discouraging long-term planning and diverting resources away from strategic development. Across countries, participants highlighted that complex or unstable legal frameworks create uncertainty and administrative burdens. Greek interviewees noted frequent changes in cooperative law that undermine long-term planning: “Every few years the law changes, and we have to start again. How can we plan for the future if the rules are never stable?” [Solution Hub Meeting – Board chair, Greece]. They also pointed to the impact of policy changes on investment decisions: “Frequent policy changes and bureaucracy discourage cooperative leaders from long-term investment and innovation.” [Interview – Policy Maker, Greece].

In Spain and France, bureaucratic hurdles in aid distribution and compliance with EU regulations were seen as particularly demanding. For example, a French expert argued, “For me, the threats are based on one fundamental thing: the assimilation of the cooperative to a private company. If we assimilate it to private companies, we deprive them of their assets. The cooperative has to keep the specific link with members, otherwise we lose a means of action to bring everyone along.” [Interview – Legal Expert, France].

In France, participants also highlighted the cumulative effects of excessive regulation, which forces cooperatives to comply with numerous rules, making them less competitive than other European producers: “Too many rules, too many regulations ... other countries in Europe are not facing such constraints.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Cooperative manager, France].

Turkish participants described excessive bureaucracy and taxation rules as slowing cooperative decision-making. As one cooperative manager noted: “The legislation is too complicated and restricts us from developing strategies ... There is also conflict between authority and duty, and the auditing mechanism doesn't work properly.” [Interview – Cooperative manager, Türkiye].

In Italy, one-size-fits-all policies were described as inefficient and unfair. For example, an Italian board chair who happens to also be a policy maker, suggested that “The wine sector is very complex, with legislation that doesn't differentiate between the north and the south. The management of replanting requires it to be done within two years, but agronomically it makes no sense without at least 3 or 4 years. These are glaring issues that create problems.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair/Policy maker, Italy]. Another cooperative leader from Italy pointed to the gap between narratives and actions: “Currently, the management of the regional plant protection service is very negative ... There's a

political narrative on sustainability, but the practical issue is vineyards dying due to flavescence dorée, and the institutions are not providing real solutions.” [Interview – Cooperative board chair, Italy].

Limited institutional support and capacity gaps. Limited institutional support and capacity gaps were framed as reinforcing existing organizational weaknesses, particularly by constraining access to training, innovation, and governance modernization. Italian cooperatives stressed the lack of resources for training and capacity-building programs, which limits their ability to modernize governance and management practices. For example, a cooperative member noted that “Training and education are crucial, but in the context of cooperatives, there's very little emphasis. Even in university programs, such as mine, which was focused on oenology, there's little to no discussion about cooperatives. Despite the fact that 60 % of Italian wine is produced by cooperatives, no one explains what a cooperative really does.” [Interview – Cooperative Member, Italy].

Similar concerns were raised in Greece, where weak institutional backing was said to constrain innovation and long-term development. A young cooperative officer from Greece suggests that “There is no real support from the state for training or modernization. We are left to solve everything ourselves, but we don't have the resources.” [Solution Hub Meeting – Cooperative officer, late 20s]. An interviewee highlighted the negative impact of a constantly changing institutional environment: “The institutional framework is unstable and creates mistrust; cooperative leaders often feel abandoned by policymakers.” [Interview – Cooperative Expert, Greece].

Land tenure and property rights issues. Land tenure and property rights constraints were interpreted as structural barriers that hinder cooperative expansion, investment, and intergenerational transfer, especially in fragmented agricultural systems. In Türkiye and Spain, participants pointed to low land mobility and land fragmentation as structural constraints that complicate cooperative expansion and investment. These institutional problems were often linked to broader rural depopulation and generational turnover challenges. In Türkiye, “There is a very messy and complicated legislation. Producer organizations operate under different laws—some under the general cooperative law, others under sector-specific rules—creating confusion and inefficiency.” [Interview – Cooperative expert, Türkiye].

Table 2 synthesizes country-specific illustrations of how organizational, market/industry, and institutional/legal challenges manifest across France, Greece, Italy, Spain, and Türkiye. The table is not intended to be exhaustive but rather to highlight illustrative examples raised by participants in Solution Hubs and interviews. Categorization follows the thematic framework introduced in Section 2, with climate change consistently placed under market/industry challenges. While many challenges overlap categories, each was assigned to the area where participants placed the strongest emphasis.

In sum, the findings highlight how organizational, market and industry, and institutional/legal challenges are deeply intertwined across Mediterranean cooperatives, though their expression varies by country. These original results provide the foundation for the following discussion, where we relate them to theoretical perspectives and existing empirical studies.

5. Discussion

5.1. Common challenges across mediterranean cooperatives

Across France, Greece, Italy, Spain, and Türkiye, agricultural cooperatives face a series of shared challenges that limit their resilience, growth, and sustainability. Based on Solution Hub discussions and interviews, these challenges specifically shed light on the situation of Mediterranean cooperatives around: organizational, market and industry-related, and institutional/legal. Together, these challenges span governance, financial stability, member engagement, environmental sustainability, workforce dynamics, innovation, and cultural

Table 2
Country-specific illustrations of challenges reported by participants.

Country	Organizational Challenges	Market & Industry Challenges	Institutional & Legal Challenges
France	Weakened member-cooperative ties; difficulty balancing professionalization with democratic governance; shortages of skilled managers	Climate change adaptation (water efficiency, carbon neutrality, biomass use); pressure from supermarket chains; limited access to affordable investment capital	Complex and frequently changing regulatory requirements; high compliance costs
Greece	Inefficient governance; weak member commitment; low trust; land fragmentation limits scale	Low product prices and rising input costs; stagnation in market expansion; limited innovation	Frequent changes in cooperative law; weak institutional support; limited infrastructure and digitalization
Italy	Communication gaps with members; limited youth involvement; succession challenges	Difficulties in adapting to global competition; supply chain inefficiencies; limited access to research and innovation	Bureaucratic hurdles; capacity constraints for training and modernization
Spain	Low member engagement; insufficient leadership succession; underrepresentation of women and youth	Severe drought and water scarcity; rural depopulation and labor shortages; need for scale and mergers to compete	Bureaucratic barriers in aid allocation; land tenure disputes; rigid bylaws reducing flexibility
Türkiye	Low trust in cooperatives; governance inefficiencies; limited entrepreneurial orientation	Market liberalization and strong competition; farm profitability pressures; climate change impacts (droughts, floods, heatwaves)	Excessive bureaucracy and taxation; political instability and policy shifts; insecure land tenure

shifts. Their recurrence across countries points to systemic and interconnected obstacles that require both cooperative-level reforms and supportive institutional frameworks. Table 3 summarizes these common challenges.

The subsequent subsections (5.2–5.4) expand on each category in greater depth and situate our findings within existing theoretical and empirical literature.

5.2. Organizational challenges

Our results on governance inefficiencies and weak member participation resonate strongly with the literature on organizational costs in cooperatives. Transaction cost theory (Coase, 1937; (Williamson, 1985)) emphasizes coordination and agency problems, while Hansmann's (1996) ownership cost approach highlights the difficulties of collective

Table 3
Common challenges facing Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives.

Category	Challenges
Organizational	1. Governance inefficiencies and lack of professionalization 2. Weak member engagement and trust 3. Slow adoption of innovation and weak strategic planning
Market & Industry	4. Low profitability and financial instability 5. Climate change impacts and resource management challenges 6. Rural depopulation and labor shortages
Institutional/ Legal	7. Generational and cultural shifts undermining cooperative sustainability

decision-making in member-owned firms. Participants' concerns about slow decision-making, weak professionalization, and fragile trust relations confirm these classic theoretical costs (e.g., Iliopoulos and Cook, 2023).

Empirical studies reinforce this interpretation. (Iliopoulos and Valentinov, 2012) documented persistent opportunism and governance weaknesses in Greek cooperatives, consistent with our participants' accounts. Giagnocavo et al. (2012) and Arcidiacono (2018) observed similar tensions between professionalization and member control in Spanish and Italian cooperatives, while Sevinç (2021) reported that governance weaknesses undermine trust and collective action in Türkiye. Global evidence also confirms these patterns: Fulton and Hueth (2009) highlighted governance-related cooperative failures in North America, and (Grashuis and Cook, 2018) showed how new-generation cooperatives collapsed when ownership and decision-making costs became unsustainable.

Our findings therefore confirm established theoretical and empirical insights into governance costs but also extend them. In the Mediterranean context, strengthening governance structures and enhancing professionalization seem to be critical objectives, while simultaneously fostering social capital and sustaining active member engagement. Participants also highlighted gender inclusivity and generational renewal as emerging governance concerns that are underdeveloped in existing literature. These factors complicate traditional accounts of ownership and decision-making costs and suggest new directions for cooperative governance research.

5.3. Market- and industry-related challenges

Market-related challenges identified by participants—such as climate change impacts, price pressures, and labor shortages—align closely with the literature on market failures and cooperative adaptation. Classic analyses (Sexton and Iskow, 1988; Cook, 1995) argue that cooperatives emerge to counterbalance oligopsony power and low farm-gate prices. Our findings confirm that financial instability, price-cost squeezes, and market volatility remain central issues, consistent with global evidence (Gray and Kraenzle, 2002; Pujara, 2016).

At the same time, our evidence extends the literature by showing how environmental and demographic pressures amplify these market failures in the Mediterranean context. Arenas-Castro et al. (2020) documented drought-related risks for Spanish olive oil cooperatives, and Özgirgin et al. (2021) showed how Turkish cooperatives face dual pressures from liberalized markets and environmental stressors. Similar vulnerabilities were observed by Pineiro et al. (2021) in Spanish cropland cooperatives. Beyond the Mediterranean, (Cook, 2018) in the U.S. and Leite et al. (2021) in Brazil demonstrated how liberalization and competitive pressures drive restructuring and test member loyalty.

Our findings confirm earlier research showing that market pressures weaken cooperative resilience, while extending this understanding by highlighting the distinctive convergence of climate change risks, rural depopulation, and challenges of generational succession in the Mediterranean. These intersecting pressures render the adaptation of cooperatives in this region both especially urgent and particularly complex.

5.4. Institutional and legal challenges

Institutional and legal barriers were consistently highlighted by participants, particularly frequent changes in cooperative law, policy uncertainty, and bureaucratic burdens. These findings resonate with institutional economics (North, 1990; Henrj, 2012), which emphasizes that effective cooperative development requires stable and supportive rules.

Empirical studies in the Mediterranean confirm these observations. Kalogiannidis et al. (2014) showed that frequent reforms in Greek cooperative law created uncertainty and limited long-term planning,

while (Hernández-Espallardo et al., 2013) found that bureaucratic burdens hindered Spanish cooperatives' access to EU aid. Filippi (2014, 2018) highlighted comparable challenges in France, and Iliopoulos (2013) emphasized how legal and organizational constraints limited Greek cooperatives' effectiveness. Global evidence offers further contrasts: Francesconi and Ruben (2012) found that African cooperatives collapsed when institutional support was withdrawn, while (Bijman, 2016) showed that stable institutions in Northern Europe enable cooperatives to adapt more effectively. Leite et al. (2021) found that institutional trust in Brazilian cooperatives reduced opportunism and strengthened resilience.

Our findings therefore confirm that unstable and burdensome institutional environments undermine cooperative resilience, but they also extend the literature by demonstrating how generational and cultural shifts intersect with legal instability. This intersection creates a distinctive Mediterranean pattern in which weak institutions compound demographic and cultural challenges, making cooperative renewal more difficult than in other regions.

5.5. Practical and policy implications

The findings of this study highlight the need for targeted, context-specific interventions to address the multifaceted challenges facing Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives. From a practical standpoint, cooperative leaders must prioritize governance modernization, member engagement, and capacity-building to enhance organizational efficiency and resilience. For instance, in France, efforts should focus on balancing modernization with cooperative principles, while in Greece, improving financial stability and member trust is critical. In Spain and Italy, addressing generational succession and youth participation in governance is essential for long-term sustainability. Capacity-building initiatives, such as leadership training programs and collaborative innovation ecosystems, can play a crucial role in equipping cooperatives to adapt to market pressures and climate challenges.

From a policy perspective, supportive legal and regulatory frameworks are essential for fostering cooperative development and sustainability. Policymakers should adopt targeted interventions tailored to the unique challenges of each country. For example, in France and Spain, financial incentives for agroecological transitions and governance training programs for young and female leaders are needed. In Greece, improving access to credit and modernizing infrastructure should be prioritized, while in Türkiye, reducing bureaucratic burdens and fostering regional collaboration are key. At the EU level, initiatives such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) could support cooperative resilience through funding for innovation, climate adaptation, and capacity-building programs. By aligning policy efforts with the specific needs of cooperatives, stakeholders can create an enabling environment that promotes sustainable rural development and strengthens the Mediterranean food system.

These recommendations provide a roadmap for cooperative leaders and policymakers to address the challenges identified in this study, fostering resilience, inclusivity, and sustainability in Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives. By implementing these strategies, stakeholders can strengthen the role of cooperatives in rural development and ensure their long-term viability in an evolving agricultural landscape.

5.6. Future research

Future research should focus on developing and evaluating context-specific, scalable interventions that address the interconnected challenges facing Mediterranean agricultural cooperatives, with an emphasis on fostering innovation, inclusivity, and resilience. Key areas include assessing the effectiveness of hybrid governance models that balance democratic principles with professional management, particularly in countries like France and Spain where modernization tensions are pronounced. Research should also explore the impact of targeted

capacity-building programs, such as leadership training for women and youth, and their role in enhancing member engagement and generational renewal, especially in Greece, Italy, France and Spain where demographic shifts are critical. Additionally, studies should investigate the potential of collaborative innovation ecosystems to overcome financial and technological barriers, as well as the role of regional knowledge-sharing platforms in promoting climate-resilient practices. Evaluating the impact of policy reforms, such as streamlined regulatory frameworks and financial incentives for agroecological transitions, could provide actionable insights for policymakers. By addressing these gaps, future research can contribute to the long-term sustainability of Mediterranean cooperatives, benefiting farmers, rural communities, and the broader food system. The Mediterranean context exacerbates the need to respond to climate change challenges by strengthening innovation and sustainability strategies. This raises questions about cooperatives as agents of change.

6. Conclusion

Agricultural cooperatives play a vital role in supporting farmers' livelihoods and rural development. Yet they face persistent organizational, market, and institutional challenges that threaten their sustainability. Despite extensive single-country studies, there has been little comparative evidence on how these challenges unfold across Mediterranean contexts.

The objective of this paper is to identify the key challenges facing agricultural cooperatives in the Mediterranean region. To achieve this, we employed an innovative qualitative methodology that integrates two complementary sources of information: findings from Solution Hubs and interviews with diverse experts. This approach ensured a comprehensive and in-depth exploration of the subject. Additionally, the methodology was applied across five countries, allowing for the consideration of country-specific cultural, market, and institutional factors in identifying these challenges.

Results highlight the multifaceted and interconnected challenges facing agricultural cooperatives across the Mediterranean region, emphasizing both shared themes and country-specific variations. While emphasis varies across countries—from governance modernization in France to legal instability in Greece and demographic challenges in Italy, Spain, and Türkiye—the overall pattern is one of systemic, interconnected pressures spanning organizational, market, and institutional domains. These variations underscore the need for context-specific strategies.

This study contributes by (i) offering a comparative analysis across five Mediterranean countries; (ii) combining participatory Solution Hubs with expert interviews to triangulate practitioner and policy insights; and (iii) extending cooperative governance and adaptation literatures by showing how governance costs intersect with demographic change, climate stress, and institutional instability in distinctive Mediterranean ways.

In summary, this research calls for capacity-building initiatives, leadership training, and organizational reforms to address governance inefficiencies, financial constraints, and innovation barriers. Policymakers must facilitate access to credit, promote inclusive governance, prevent climate change and foster regional cooperation, but without all this creating a bureaucratic burden that threatens the survival of cooperatives. Ultimately, addressing these challenges requires a balanced approach that combines regional cooperation, targeted interventions, and capacity-building to empower cooperatives in driving sustainable rural development. This study lays the groundwork for future research and action, emphasizing the need for holistic, context-aware strategies in an evolving agricultural landscape, consistent with the FAO's resilience framework, which highlights economic viability, environmental stewardship, and social inclusion.

While these contributions are significant, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the qualitative design, based primarily on Solution

Hubs and semi-structured interviews, captures rich, context-specific perspectives but limits the generalizability of findings to the wider population of cooperatives. Second, although efforts were made to ensure diversity in participants, the sample size remains modest and may not fully represent the heterogeneity of cooperative forms and sectors in each country. Third, the participatory nature of Solution Hubs carries potential biases, such as dominance of certain voices or group dynamics influencing responses. Finally, the study focused on identifying challenges rather than systematically exploring opportunities or solutions, which suggests avenues for further research. These limitations underline the need for complementary quantitative studies and longitudinal approaches to validate and extend the findings presented here, without calling into question the results of this initial exploratory study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Constantine Iliopoulos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Irini Theodorakopoulou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Manuel Gonzalez Diaz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation. **Maryline Filippi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Umberto Nizza:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Arzu Tektas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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